

MAHARAJA NIM: WYTHOFF'S QUEEN MEETS THE KNIGHT**Urban Larsson**

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Abstract

We introduce the impartial game of *Maharaja Nim*, an extension of the classical game of Wythoff Nim. In the latter game, two players take turns in moving a single Queen of Chess on a large board, attempting to be the first to put her in the lower left corner, position $(0,0)$. Here, in addition to the classical rules, a player may also move the Queen as the Knight of Chess moves, still taking into consideration that, by moving no coordinate increases. We prove that the second player's winning positions are close to those of Wythoff Nim, namely, they are within a bounded distance to the half-lines, starting at the origin, of slope $\frac{\sqrt{5}+1}{2}$ and $\frac{\sqrt{5}-1}{2}$ respectively. This result is made possible via a generalization of a recent result of Fraenkel and Peled on complementary sequences of positive integers, and via an encoding of the patterns of P-positions by means of a certain *dictionary process*; thus we here also present two methods for analyzing games related to Wythoff Nim. Via Post's tag productions, we also prove that, in general, such dictionary processes are algorithmically undecidable.

1. Maharaja Nim

We introduce a 2-player combinatorial game called *Maharaja Nim*, which is an extension of the well-known game of Wythoff Nim [17]. The name Maharaja is

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taken from a variation of Chess, “The Maharaja and the Sepoys” [4]. Both games are impartial, that is, the move options are the same regardless of whose turn it is. See [1] for a background on impartial games.

We let \mathbb{N} and \mathbb{N}_0 denote the positive and nonnegative integers respectively. It is convenient to label our positions by ordered pairs of nonnegative integers. Place a *Queen of Chess* on a given position (x, y) , $x, y \in \mathbb{N}_0$, of a large (Chess) board, with the position in the lower left corner the unique terminal position, labeled $(0, 0)$. In the game of Wythoff Nim, here denoted by W, the two players move the Queen alternately as it moves in Chess, but with the restriction that, by moving, no coordinate increases; see Figure 1. A player who cannot move, because the position is $(0, 0)$, loses. This variation of Wythoff Nim is called “Corner the Queen” and was invented by R. P. Isaacs in 1960. In Maharaja Nim, denoted by M, the rules are as in Wythoff Nim, except that the Queen is exchanged for a *Maharaja*, a piece which is moved either as the Queen or the *Knight* of Chess, again, provided by moving no coordinate increases; see Figure 1. Hence, for $x, y \in \mathbb{N}_0$, we get that, if (x, y) is a given position of Wythoff Nim, then its *options* are of the forms $(x, y - r)$, $(x - s, y)$ and $(x - t, y - t)$, for $0 < r \leq y$, $0 < s \leq x$ and $0 < t \leq \min\{x, y\}$ respectively. For Maharaja Nim the two options $(x - 1, y - 2)$ and $(x - 2, y - 1)$ are also available, provided the respective coordinates are nonnegative.

Figure 1: The move options, from a given position, of Wythoff Nim and Maharaja Nim respectively.

As usual, for impartial games, we denote a position by P if the second player has a winning strategy, and N otherwise. Similar to Wythoff Nim, Maharaja Nim terminates in a finite number of moves so that the sets of P- and N-positions partition the set of starting positions. We let \mathcal{P}_M and \mathcal{P}_W denote the set of P-positions of Maharaja Nim and Wythoff Nim respectively. See Figure 2 for a computation of the initial P-positions of the respective games.

Let $\phi = \frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2}$ denote the *Golden ratio*. Wythoff Nim’s set of P-positions is

$$\mathcal{P}_W = \{(\lfloor \phi n \rfloor, \lfloor \phi^2 n \rfloor), (\lfloor \phi^2 n \rfloor, \lfloor \phi n \rfloor) \mid n \in \mathbb{N}_0\}; \tag{1}$$

see paper [17]. From this it follows that there is precisely one P-position of Wythoff Nim in each row and each column of the board; see also paper [2].

The purpose of this paper is to explore the P-positions of Maharaja Nim. In particular we are interested in their relation to the Golden ratio. In a sense, we will prove that the (asymptotic) behavior of the P-positions of Wythoff Nim remains stable when the Knight type moves are adjoined to those of the Queen, namely, they will remain ‘close’ to the half-lines, starting at the origin, of slope ϕ^{-1} and ϕ respectively; see Figure 3. We let $O(1)$ denote bounded functions on \mathbb{N}_0 .

Theorem 1.1 (Main Theorem). *Each P-position of Maharaja Nim lies on one of the stripes $\phi x + O(1)$ or $\phi^{-1}x + O(1)$, that is, if $(x, y) \in \mathcal{P}_M$, with $y \geq x$, then $y - \phi x$ is $O(1)$.*

We prove this result in Section 3, by encoding the patterns of the P-positions by means of a certain *dictionary process*, a variation of the well known Fibonacci morphism. This result is preceded by some general properties of our games, as well as a number theoretical Central Lemma in Section 2. In Section 4, we finish off by proving that our dictionary processes are in general algorithmically undecidable.

Figure 2: The pictures represent the initial P-positions of Wythoff Nim and Maharaja Nim respectively. See also Table 1 on page 9.

2. Complementary Sequences and a Central Lemma

Let us begin by discussing some of the main properties of the P-positions of our games. Clearly $(0, 0)$ is P. Another trivial observation is that, since the rules of game are symmetric, if (x, y) is P then (y, x) is P. It is also easy to see that there is at

Figure 3: The P-positions of Wythoff Nim lie on the half-lines ϕx and $\phi^{-1}x$, $x \geq 0$. To the right, the picture illustrates a main result of this paper, that the P-positions of Maharaja Nim are bounded below and above by the stripes $y = \phi x + O(1)$ and $y = \phi^{-1}x + O(1)$ respectively.

most one P-position in each row and each column (corresponding to the Rook-type moves). But, in fact, the same assertion as for Wythoff Nim holds:

Proposition 2.1. *There is precisely one P-position of Maharaja Nim in each row and each column of $\mathbb{N}_0 \times \mathbb{N}_0$.*

Proof. Let $k \in \mathbb{N}_0$. Since all Nim-type moves are allowed in Maharaja Nim, there is at most one P-position in each column (and row) of $\mathbb{N}_0 \times \mathbb{N}_0$. This implies that there are at most k P-positions strictly to the left of the k th column (row), which is trivially true for $k = 0$. Each such P-position is an option for at most three N-positions in column (row) k . This implies that there is a least position in column (row) k which has only N-positions as options. By definition this position is P and so, since k is an arbitrary index, the result follows. \square

Another claim (corresponding to the Bishop type moves) holds for both Wythoff Nim and Maharaja Nim. There is at most one P-position on each *diagonal* of the form

$$\{(x, x + C) \mid x \in \mathbb{N}_0\}, C \in \mathbb{N}_0. \tag{2}$$

We call (2) the C th *diagonal*, and $C > 0$ corresponds to an *upper diagonal*. By symmetry, the result also holds for negative values of C (and hence for each lower diagonal).

For Wythoff Nim, (1) readily gives that there is *precisely* one P-position on each such diagonal, and even more; if

$$\mathcal{P}_W = \{(a_i, b_i), (b_i, a_i)\}, \tag{3}$$

with (a_i) increasing and for all i , $a_i \leq b_i$, then for all n ,

$$\{0, 1, \dots, n\} = \{b_i - a_i \mid i \in \{0, 1, \dots, n\}\}. \tag{4}$$

As we will see later in this section, a somewhat weaker, but crucial, property also holds for Maharaja Nim.

We say that two sequences of positive integers are *complementary* if each positive integer is contained precisely once in exactly one of these sequences. In [5] the authors prove the following result.

Proposition 2.2 (Fraenkel, Peled). *Suppose (x_n) and (y_n) are complementary and increasing sequences of positive integers. Suppose further that there is a positive real constant, δ , such that, for all n ,*

$$y_n - x_n = \delta n + O(1). \tag{5}$$

Then there are constants, $1 < \alpha < 2 < \beta$, such that, for all n ,

$$x_n - \alpha n = O(1) \tag{6}$$

and

$$y_n - \beta n = O(1). \tag{7}$$

Since, as we will see, the y -sequence of Maharaja Nim’s P-positions is not increasing, we cannot use this proposition directly. However, we have found a simplified proof of an extension of this result.

By simple density estimates one may decide the constants α and β , in Proposition 2.2, as functions of δ . Namely, notice that (5), (6) and (7) together imply

$$\beta = \alpha + \delta \tag{8}$$

and, by complementarity, we must have

$$\frac{1}{\alpha} + \frac{1}{\beta} = 1. \tag{9}$$

(Thus α and β are algebraic numbers if and only if δ is.) By this we get the relation

$$\delta(1 - \alpha) + \alpha = (\alpha - 1)\alpha, \tag{10}$$

which will turn out useful. If we let

$$\mathcal{P}_M = \{(a_n, b_n), (b_n, a_n) \mid n \in \mathbb{N}_0\}, \tag{11}$$

with (a_n) increasing and for all $n, b_n \geq a_n$, then, for all n, b_n is uniquely defined by the rules of M. At this point, one might want to observe that, if the b -sequence would have been increasing (by Figure 2 it is not) then Theorem 1.1 would follow from Proposition 2.2 if one could only establish the following claim: $b_n - a_n - n$ is $O(1)$. Namely, in (10) $\delta = 1$ gives $\alpha = \phi$ in Proposition 2.2. Now, interestingly enough, it turns out that Proposition 2.2 holds without the condition that the y -sequence be increasing; namely, (5) together with an increasing x -sequence suffices.

Lemma 2.3 (Central Lemma). *Suppose (x_n) and (y_n) are complementary sequences of positive integers with (x_n) increasing. Suppose further that there is a positive real constant, δ , such that, for all n ,*

$$y_n - x_n = \delta n + O(1). \tag{12}$$

Then there are constants, $1 < \alpha < 2 < \beta$, such that, for all n ,

$$x_n - \alpha n = O(1) \tag{13}$$

and

$$y_n - \beta n = O(1). \tag{14}$$

Proof. We begin by demonstrating that, for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$x_{n+1} = x_n + O(1), \tag{15}$$

and

$$y_{n+1} = y_n + O(1). \tag{16}$$

By (12), for all $k, n \in \mathbb{N}$ we have that

$$\begin{aligned} y_{n+k} - y_n &= x_{n+k} + \delta(n+k) - x_n - \delta n + O(1), \\ &= x_{n+k} - x_n + \delta k + O(1). \end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

Since, for all $k, n \in \mathbb{N}$, $x_{n+k} - x_n \geq k$ and $\delta > 0$ this means that, for all $k, n \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$y_{n+k} \geq y_n - C, \tag{18}$$

where C is some universal positive constant (which may depend on δ). But, with C as in (18), we can find another universal constant $\kappa = \kappa(C) \in \mathbb{N}$ such that, for all n ,

$$y_{n+\kappa} - y_n \geq \kappa + 2C + 1. \tag{19}$$

This follows since, in (17), for any C , we can find $k = k(C)$ such that, for all n , $\delta k + O(1) > 2C$. Any such k suffices as our κ . On the one hand there can be at most $\kappa - 1$ numbers from the y -sequence strictly between y_n and $y_{n+\kappa}$ (with indexes strictly between n and $n + \kappa$). On the other hand the inequality (18) gives that there can be at most C numbers from the y -sequence with index greater than $n + \kappa$, but less than $y_{n+\kappa}$. It also gives that there can be at most C numbers with index less than n but greater than y_n . Therefore, by complementarity and (19), there has to be a number from the x -sequence in every interval of length $\kappa + 2C + 1$. Thus the jumps in the x -sequence are bounded, which is (15). But then (16) follows from (12) and (15), since

$$\begin{aligned} y_{n+1} - y_n &= x_{n+1} + \delta(n + 1) - x_n - \delta n + O(1) \\ &= x_{n+1} + \delta - x_n + O(1) \\ &= O(1). \end{aligned}$$

By (16), we may define m as a function of n with

$$x_n = y_m + O(1). \tag{20}$$

(For example, one can take $m = m(n)$ the least number such that $x_n < y_m$. Then $y_m - x_n$ has to be bounded for otherwise $y_m - y_{m-1}$ is not bounded.) This has two consequences, of which the first one is

$$x_n = n + m + O(1). \tag{21}$$

This follows since the numbers $1, 2, \dots, x_n$ are partitioned in n numbers from the x -sequence, and the rest, by complementarity, $m + O(1)$ numbers from the y -sequence.

The second consequence of (20) is that, by using (12),

$$x_n = x_m + \delta m + O(1). \tag{22}$$

If $\lim x_n/n$ and $\lim y_n/n$ exist, then clearly they must satisfy (8) and (9) with δ as in the lemma. Thus, using this definition of $\alpha = \alpha(\delta)$, for all n , let

$$\Delta_n = x_n - \alpha n.$$

We want to use (21) and (22) to express Δ_n in terms of Δ_m .

Equation (22) expresses x_n in terms of x_m and m . Therefore, we wish to combine (21) and (22) to express n in terms of x_m and m , that is, we wish to eliminate x_n from (21). If we plug in the expression (22) for x_n in (21) and solve for n we get

$$n = x_m + (\delta - 1)m + O(1). \tag{23}$$

Combining (22) and (23) gives

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_n &= x_m + \delta m - \alpha(x_m + (\delta - 1)m) + O(1) \\ &= (1 - \alpha)x_m + (\delta(1 - \alpha) + \alpha)m + O(1) \\ &= (1 - \alpha)\Delta_m + O(1), \end{aligned} \tag{24}$$

where the last equality is by (10).

Notice that, by (22), for sufficiently large n we have that $m < n$. Hence we may use strong induction and by (24) conclude that Δ_n is $O(1)$ which is (13). Then (14) follows from (12). \square

3. Perfect Sectors, a Dictionary, and the Proof of Theorem 1.1

This section is devoted to the proof of Theorem 1.1. We begin by proving that there is precisely one P-position of Maharaja Nim on each diagonal of the form in (2). Then we explain how the proof of this result leads to the second part of the theorem, the bounding of the P-positions within the desired *stripes* (Figure 3).

A position, say (x, y) , is an *upper* position if it is strictly above the *main diagonal*, that is if $y > x$; otherwise it is *lower*. We call a (C, x) -*perfect sector*, or simply a *perfect sector*, all positions strictly above the C th diagonal, of the form in (2), and strictly to the right of column x .

Suppose that we have computed all P-positions in the columns $1, 2, \dots, a_{n-1}$ and that, when we erase each upper position from which a player can move to an upper P-position in one of these columns, then the remaining upper positions strictly to the right of column a_{n-1} constitute the $(n - 1, a_{n-1})$ -perfect sector (Figure 4 to the right). Then we say that (column) a_{n-1} is *perfect* and, in fact, it is easy to see that also property (4) holds for all such n . As we will see, it is essential to our approach that, for any such n ,

$$b_n - a_n = n \tag{25}$$

(whenever lower P-positions do not interfere).

Let us list the initial P-positions (a_n, b_n) of Maharaja Nim together with the differences $b_n - a_n$.

Lemma 3.1. *Suppose that $n \in \mathbb{N}$ is sufficiently large so that Knight type moves from lower P-positions do not interfere with the upper positions and define (a_i) and (b_i) as in (11). Suppose further that a_{n-1} is perfect. Then*

$$\{0, 1, \dots, n - 1\} = \{b_i - a_i \mid 0 \leq i < n\} \tag{26}$$

and (25) holds.

$\lfloor \phi^2 n \rfloor$	0	2	5	7	10	13	15	18	20	23	26	28	31	34	36	39
$\lfloor \phi n \rfloor$	0	1	3	4	6	8	9	11	12	14	16	17	19	21	22	24
b_n	0	3	6	5	10	13	16	19	18	23	26	29	30	34	37	41
a_n	0	1	2	4	7	8	9	11	12	14	15	17	20	21	22	24
$b_n - a_n$	0	2	4	1	3	5	7	8	6	9	11	12	10	13	15	17
n	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15

Table 1: This is a list of the initial P-positions (a_n, b_n) of Maharaja Nim together with the differences $b_n - a_n$. We compare with the P-positions of Wythoff Nim on top. We also *emphasize* when column a_{n-1} is perfect (implying $b_n - a_n = n$).

Proof. There are precisely $n - 1$ upper P-positions, strictly to the left of column a_{n-1} . Since column a_{n-1} is perfect, they produce precisely $n - 1$ upper diagonals of N-positions between the perfect sector and the 0th diagonal. Hence (26) holds. Further, there is no upper P-position to the left of the a_n th column that interferes with the perfect sector via a Knight type move, because then the sector would not have been perfect. Hence, by definition of P, since the n th upper diagonal is free, the position $(a_n, a_n + n) \in \mathcal{P}_M$. This gives $b_n = a_n + n$ so that (25) holds. \square

We will adjoin a new *word* to Maharaja Nim’s *dictionary* if and only if the conditions in this lemma are satisfied. Let us proceed to explain this construction. See also Section 4 for a brief general discussion of such dictionary processes.

3.1. Constructing Maharaja Nim’s Bit-String

We study a bit-string, a sequence of ‘0’s and ‘1’s, where the i th bit equals ‘0’ if and only if there is an upper P-position of Maharaja Nim in column i . By Proposition 2.1, if there is no upper P-position in column i , there is a lower ditto (the i th bit equals ‘1’).

Suppose (as an induction hypothesis) that column $n - 1$ is perfect. Then, by symmetry, we know some lower P-positions in columns to the right of n . The next step is to erase each column in the perfect sector for which there is currently a lower P-position, a ‘1’ in the bit-string; see Figure 5.

Then, recursively in the non-erased part of the perfect sector, we compute new upper P-positions until we reach the next perfect sector (for the moment assume that this will happen) at say the perfect column $n - 1 + m$, $m > 0$. Thus, using this notation, we define a *word*, say w , of length m , containing the information of whether the P-position in column $i \in \{n, n + 1, \dots, n + m - 1\}$ is below or above the main diagonal.

At this point we adjoin this word w together with its unique *translate*, $D(w)$, to Maharaja Nim’s dictionary. The translate is obtained accordingly: for each P-position in the columns n to $n + m - 1$ define the i th bit in $D(w)$ as a ‘1’ if and only

Figure 4: The left most picture shows $(0,0)$ together with the 7 first upper P-positions of Maharaja Nim (see also Figure 2 and Table 1). All upper positions from which a player can move to one of these P-positions are erased. The remaining ‘sector’ is not perfect. To the right, the $(8,13)$ -perfect sector has been detected. Namely, the lowest non-erased diagonal from the picture to the left is cancelled by introducing the 8th upper P-position.

if row $k + i$ has an upper P-position and where k is the largest row index strictly below the perfect sector. See also Figure 6, where $k = 12$ in the leftmost picture. The translate $D(w)$ will have length $m+l$, where l denotes the number of ‘0’s in the word w . This follows since, by counting diagonals, a new perfect sector will start in the position $(n + m, k + m + l + 1)$. Since the l th P-position (in case $l > 0$) will not correspond to the upper most P-position, $D(w)$ will end with at least 2 ‘0’s.

We then concatenate the translate, $D(w)$, at the end of the existing bit-string. In this way, provided a next perfect sector will be detected, the bit-string will always grow faster than we read from it. However, there is no immediate guarantee that we will be able to repeat the procedure—that the next word exists—or for that matter that the size of the dictionary will be finite, so that the process may be described by a finite system of words and translates. But, in what follows, we aim to prove that, in fact, the next perfect sector will always (in the sense outlined above) be detected within a ‘period’ of at most 7 upper P-positions, that is ‘0’s in the bit-string. As we will see, a complete dictionary needs only (between 9 and) 14 translations.

In this context it is interesting to observe that for Wythoff Nim, \mathcal{P}_W can be derived from the dictionary $0 \rightarrow 10$ and $1 \rightarrow 0$. Namely, starting at the first column, the word begins $01001010\dots$; that is, it is identical to the infinite Fibonacci word, corresponding to the well known Fibonacci morphism. Wythoff’s sequences as algebraic words are also studied in, e.g., [7] and their connections to further

Figure 5: This picture provides the continuation of Figure 4 in the process of detecting the words and translations of Maharaja Nim’s dictionary. Each column in the perfect sector which corresponds to a lower P-position (a ‘1’ in the bit-string 001011...) has been erased. The computation of the next few P-positions and the corresponding translation is provided in the right most picture in Figure 6.

combinatorial games in [6, 3, 8]. Let us, via an initial example, describe how Maharaja Nim’s bit-string is constructed.

3.2. The First Translations

Initially, there is some interference which does not allow a recursive definition of words and translates; see Figure 2. The first perfect sector beyond the origin is attained when the 4 first P-positions strictly above the main diagonal have been computed. This happens in column 8. There is only one P-position below the main diagonal, corresponding to a 1 in the current bit-string. It will erase column 10 in the perfect sector as indicated in the left picture in Figure 6. Then to the right of column 12 a new perfect sector will be detected. Thus the first word (left hand side entry) in the dictionary will be $w = 00100$ (the left picture in Figure 6), corresponding to the P-positions (8, 13), (9, 16), (10, 7), (11, 19) and (12, 18).

Let us verify that this word translates to $D(w) = 100101100$. Notice that the first ‘1’-bit in $D(w)$ means that the P-position (8, 13) is to the left of the main

Figure 6: To the left, the upper P-positions of Maharaja Nim in columns 8 to 12 have been computed, beginning with position (8, 13), and a perfect sector has been detected. The corresponding translation is $00100 \rightarrow 100101100$. In column 13 the translation is $1 \rightarrow 0$. The picture to the right provides the continuation of Figure 5; the upper P-positions in columns 14 to 20 have been computed, beginning with position (14, 23). One can easily check (Table 1) that at this point we have a new perfect sector and so the next translation is $0010110 \rightarrow 10010011000$.

diagonal; by symmetry this will correspond to a lower P-position in column 13. The second bit in w is ‘0’. This means that the next upper P-position is in column 14. Then, by rules of game, it has to be at least in row 16, which indeed will be attained, so that the next P-position will be (9, 16). In fact, by (26), the rows 14 and 15 cannot have P-positions to the left of the main diagonal, so that a prefix of the translate $D(w)$ is ‘1001’. Similarly, by computing the rest of the P-position of this word, we extend the prefix to ‘1001011’. Notice that the next upper P-position will be at least in row 22 since the least unused diagonal is $22 - 13 = 9$; in fact, it will be in row 23 since there is a lower P-position in column 13. This gives the last two ‘0’s in the translate, ‘100101100’ (with notation as in Section 3.1, note here that $m = 5$ and $l = 4$, so the length of the translate is correct), which may now be concatenated to the end of the prefix ‘00100’.

Thus, the new prefix is ‘00100100101100’, and the next word, to be included to the dictionary, will be the underlined ‘1’ (by symmetry, corresponding to a lower P-position in column 13). It translates to ‘0’ since no upper P-position can belong to row 22, by (26). Then, by the right picture in Figure 6, the next word to be included to the dictionary will be detected as ‘0010110’ and translated to $D(0010110) = 10010011000$. Concatenating the 2 new translates gives ‘0010010010110010010011000’, where the underlined ‘0’ is where the next word starts, and so on.

3.3. Maharaja Nim's Dictionary

Maharaja Nim's dictionary is

- $1 \rightarrow 0$ (27)
- $01 \rightarrow 100$ (28)
- $00100 \rightarrow 100101100$ (29)
- $00110 \rightarrow 10010100$ (30)
- $000100 \rightarrow 10010110100$ (31)
- $001110 \rightarrow 100100100$ (32)
- $0010110 \rightarrow 10010011000$ (33)
- $00000100 \rightarrow 100101100111000$ (34)
- $000010010 \rightarrow 1001001111000100$ (35)
- $0000000 \rightarrow 10010110110100$ (36)
- $0010100 \rightarrow 100100110100$ (37)
- $0011110 \rightarrow 1001000100$ (38)
- $00000010 \rightarrow 100101101100100$ (39)
- $00001000 \rightarrow 100100111100100$ (40)

By computer simulations we have verified that each one of the words (27) to (35) does appear in Maharaja Nim's bit-string. We have included the code in the Appendix. By our method of proof, we have found no way to exclude the latter five, but a guess is that they do not appear. At least they do not appear among the first 20000 bits of the bit-string. The following result gives the first part of the Main Theorem.

Lemma 3.2 (Completeness Lemma). *When we read from Maharaja Nim's bit-string each prefix is contained in our extended dictionary of (left hand side) words of Maharaja Nim.*

Proof. Let us present a list in lexicographic order of all words in our extended dictionary, together with the words we need to exclude. We cannot translate words that do not appear to the left in our dictionary, and hence we need to verify that they do not appear in Maharaja Nim's infinite bit-string.

- $0000000 \rightarrow 10010110110100$
- $00000010 \rightarrow 100101101100100$
- 00000011 'to exclude' (a)
- $00000100 \rightarrow 100101100111000$
- 00000101 'to exclude' (b)
- 0000011 'to exclude' (c)
- $00001000 \rightarrow 100100111100100$

000010010 \rightarrow 1001001111000100
 000010011 'to exclude' (d)
 0000101 'to exclude' (e)
 000011 'to exclude' (f)
 000100 \rightarrow 10010110100
 000101 'to exclude' (g)
 00011 'to exclude' (h)
 00100 \rightarrow 100101100
 0010100 \rightarrow 1001001110100
 0010101 'to exclude' (i)
 0010110 \rightarrow 10010011000
 0010111 'to exclude' (j)
 00110 \rightarrow 10010100
 001110 \rightarrow 100100100
 0011110 \rightarrow 1001000100
 0011111 'to exclude' (k)
 01 \rightarrow 100
 1 \rightarrow 0

This list is complete in the sense that any bit-string has precisely one of the words on the left hand side as a prefix. This motivates why it suffices to exclude the words 'to exclude'. For example (a) needs to be excluded since the *only* word in our list beginning with '0000001' continues with a '0'. Neither can we translate words beginning with '000001', and continuing with '01' or '1'. This motivates why we need to exclude (b) and (c). All left hand side words in our dictionary beginning with 4 '0's continue with 100, which motivates that (e) and (f) need to be excluded, and so on. We move on to verify that the strings (a) to (k) are not contained in the bit-string.

No translate contains more than three consecutive '0's. To get a longer string of consecutive '0's one has to finish off one translate and start anew. The only translate starting with '0' is '0'. Thus, when a sequence of four or more '0's is interrupted it means that a new translate has begun. But all translates that begin with a '1' begin with '100'. Thus, a sequence of 4 or more '0's cannot be followed by '11' or '101'. This gives that the exclusion of the words (a),(b), (c), (e) and (f) is correct.

For the same reason, the string '100' in (d) has to be the prefix of some translate. Since the next two bits are '11', by the dictionary, this translate has to be '100'. But then the next translate has the prefix '11', which is impossible.

For the exclusion of (g) and (h), notice that any time three consecutive '0's appear, within a translate or between two translates, they are followed by the string '100'. Therefore, a string of three '0's cannot be followed by '11' or '101'.

For (i), notice that the sub-string '101010' is not contained in any translate. If

it were, it needed to be either at the beginning of a translate, which is impossible (since all of them except ‘0’ begin with ‘100’), or be split between two. The latter is impossible since all translates except ‘0’ end with ‘00’. In analogy to this, (j) must also be excluded and similarly for (k), since no translate contains 5 consecutive ‘1’s and all translates end in a ‘0’, but start with either ‘0’ or ‘10’. \square

Proof. (of Theorem 1.1) By Lemma 3.2, our dictionary is correct. Since the left-hand side words have at most 7 ‘0’s, we adjoin at most 6 P-positions in a sequence with $b_n - a_n$ distinct from n . Namely, by Lemma 3.1, when we start a new perfect sector, we know that the next P-position will satisfy $b_n - a_n = n$. The number of bits in a translate is bounded (by 16) so that b_n can never deviate more than a bounded number of positions from $a_n + n$. Hence, by Proposition 2.1, the conditions of Lemma 2.3 are satisfied with the a -sequence as x , the b -sequence as y and $\delta = 1$; that is $b_n - a_n - n$ is $O(n)$ (as is also discussed in the paragraph before Lemma 2.3), which concludes the proof of Theorem 1.1. \square

By inspecting the dictionary one can see that, in fact, for all n , $-4 \leq b_n - a_n - n \leq 3$. Given this tight bound, the result in this section is quite satisfactory, but for the two gamesters trying to figure out how to quickly find safe positions, it does not quite suffice. The following question is left open.

Question 1. *Does Maharaja Nim’s decision problem, to determine whether a given position (x, y) , with input length $\log(xy)$, is P, have polynomial time complexity in $\log(xy)$?*

We resolve this question for a similar game in [12]; see also Figure 7. In Figures 8 and 9 we finish off with some questions regarding variations of Maharaja Nim, but let us first briefly discuss another problem related to the method used in this paper.

4. Dictionary Processes and Undecidability

Given a dictionary of binary words and translations, and a starting string, will the translation process of the bit-string terminate? More precisely, let us assume that we have a finite list of words $A = \{A_1, A_2, \dots, A_m\}$ with translates B_1, B_2, \dots, B_m respectively, each word being a string of ‘0’s and ‘1’s, and where we, for simplicity, assume that none of the words in A is a prefix of another.

Take any finite bit-string S as a starting string (for example A_1 but it could be an arbitrary string, not necessarily in the list). A *read head* ‘.’ starts to read S from left to the right and as soon as it finds a string A_i in A it stops, sends a signal to a printer at the other end which concatenates the translation B_i at the end of S . Then the read head continues to read from where it ended until it finds the next word in A , its translation being concatenated at the end, and so on.

If the read head gets to the end of the string without finding a word in the list A , the process stops with the current string as output. Otherwise, the process continues and gives as output an infinite string.

It follows from E. Post's *tag productions* [14, 15, 16] that our dictionary process is Turing complete. Let us include the very short proof. (Another proof is available in an extended version of this paper [12].)

Theorem 4.1. *It is algorithmically undecidable whether a given prefix-free dictionary process on a given initial string terminates.*

Proof. Let S be a finite string of letters from the alphabet $A = \{a_1, \dots, a_n\}$ and let W be an associated list of words on this alphabet, say w_1, \dots, w_n . By [15, page 2] it is undecidable whether the following tag production terminates. We read the first letter of S , say a_i , then erase the first two letters from S , and at last attach the word w_i at the end of S . Continue by performing the same operation on the resulting string. This production terminates if and only if, at some stage, the string consists of at most one letter.

Thus, to prove that it is undecidable whether our dictionary process terminates, it suffices to simulate this tag production. By using binary words, each of length precisely $\lceil \log_2 n \rceil$ (fill out with zeros if needed), we can code each $a_i \in A$ as the binary representation of $i - 1 \in \{0, \dots, n - 1\}$. Our dictionary will consist of all left hand side words of the form $(i - 1)x$, with $i - 1, x \in \{0, \dots, n - 1\}$ represented in binary, of length precisely $2\lceil \log_2 n \rceil$. (That is x is concatenated to the right of $(i - 1)$.) The x will correspond to the letter in A that the tag production erases. In the dictionary process it will obviously not be erased. Rather, via our translation rules, it will be ignored and the read head will be placed on the bit immediately to the right of its last digit. Each translation in the dictionary will be chosen to interpret only to the first $\lceil \log_2 n \rceil$ letters. The translates for the dictionary process, to be concatenated to the right of the existing string, will be the corresponding binary interpretation of each word $w_i \in W$; say if $w_2 = a_1 a_5 a_8$ with $n = 8$ then, for any x , the dictionary's corresponding translate is '001x' \rightarrow '000 100 111'. Therefore this dictionary process will terminate if and only if the tag production will. \square

In view of this result, one would like to know whether any suitable family of Maharaja Nim type games is also Turing complete. But we do not yet know whether such a family exists. However, see also recent results in [10, 13], where we reduce typical pattern-detecting problems from Turing complete one-dimensional cellular automata to, for example, the problem of P-equivalence for combinatorial games. Let us introduce the perhaps most natural candidate in the context of this paper. There are infinitely many relatives to Maharaja Nim of the form: adjoin a finite list L of move options to Wythoff Nim, $(l_1, l_2) \in L$ if and only if $(x, y) \rightarrow (x - l_1, y - l_2)$ is a legal move, for all positions (x, y) such that $x - l_1 \geq 0$ and $y - l_2 \geq 0$. It is easy to see that Proposition 2.1 and (2) hold also for these extensions of Wythoff Nim. For any given such generalization, is it possible to determine the greatest departure from n for $b_n - a_n$? Even simpler, is it decidable, whether there is a P-position above some straight line?

Question 2. *Given the moves of Wythoff Nim together with some finite list L of moves, that is ordered pairs of integers (in Maharaja Nim the list is $\{(1, 2), (2, 1)\}$),*

and a linear inequality in two variables x and y , is it decidable whether there is a P -position in the game which satisfies the inequality?

Of course, it is not even clear whether a given finite generalization of Maharaja Nim (with $(l_1, l_2) \in L$ if and only if $(l_2, l_1) \in L$) will produce a finite dictionary in the sense of Section 2; see also [12], where we study a similar but *non-prefix free dictionary* for the game where $L = \{(2, 3), (3, 2)\}$. We finish with three figures, motivating further study of extensions of Wythoff Nim and possible coding to dictionary processes whenever applicable.

Figure 7: Is it possible to decide in polynomial time, whether a given position is P for Maharaja Nim? A ‘telescope’ with focus $O(1)$ and reflectors along the lines ϕn and n/ϕ attempts to determine the outcome (P or N) of some position, (x, y) at the top of the picture. The method is successful for a similar game called $(2,3)$ -Maharaja Nim [12]. (It gives the correct value for all extensions of Wythoff Nim with a finite non-terminating converging dictionary.) The focus is kept sufficiently wide (a constant) to provide correct translations in each step. The number of steps is linear in $\log(xy)$.

Figure 8: These pictures illustrate the initial P-positions (the coordinates are less than 100) of (k, l) -Maharaja Nim, defined by $L = \{(k, l), (l, k)\}$, for $(k, l) = (3, 5), (4, 6), (4, 7), (5, 8), (6, 10)$ and $(7, 11)$ respectively. We believe that the global behavior is the same for many such games, namely, computer simulations suggest that the ratios of the respective coordinates closely approximate either ϕ or $1/\phi$. In fact the distribution along these lines appear uniform, but we have not yet been able to establish a finite dictionary for any of these games. (For many other values, such as $(k, l) = (4, 5)$, the P-positions are in fact identical to those of Wythoff Nim, e.g. [9]).

Figure 9: The initial P-positions (the coordinates are less than 1500) of four extensions of Maharaja Nim, where the adjoined moves of Wythoff Nim are $L = \{(t, 2t), (2t, t) \mid t \in S\}$, where $S = \{1, 2, \dots, 10\}$, $\{1, 2, \dots, 50\}$, $\{1, 2, \dots, 100\}$ and \mathbb{N} respectively. Notice the emerging ‘bounded split’ of the (upper) P-positions in the 2nd and 3rd picture. The ratio of the coordinates still seem to be within a bounded distance to ϕ . If so, is it possible to give this distance as an explicit function of $\max S$? But, in the last picture where an infinite number of moves are adjoined, the convergence to ϕ disappears, which is proved in [9]; in fact a non-bounded ‘split’ is established in [11].

Appendix

This code explores whether the first 9 words in Maharaja Nim's dictionary suffice.

```
dictionary:={ [1], [0,1], [0,0,1,0,0], [0,0,1,0,1,1,0], [0,0,1,1,0],
[0,0,0,1,0,0], [0,0,0,0,1,0,0,1,0], [0,0,0,0,0,1,0,0], [0,0,1,1,1,0] };

translation:=table([ [1]=[0], [0,1]=[1,0,0], [0,0,1,0,0]=[1,0,0,1,0,1,1,0,0],
[0,0,1,0,1,1,0]=[1,0,0,1,0,0,1,1,0,0,0], [0,0,1,1,0]=[1,0,0,1,0,1,0,0],
[0,0,0,1,0,0]=[1,0,0,1,0,1,1,0,1,0,0],
[0,0,0,0,1,0,0,1,0]=[1,0,0,1,0,0,1,1,1,1,0,0,0,1,0,0],
[0,0,0,0,0,1,0,0]=[1,0,0,1,0,1,1,0,0,1,1,1,0,0,0],
[0,0,1,1,1,0]=[1,0,0,1,0,0,1,0,0] ]);

theString:=[0,0,1,0,0]: reader:=0:
for times to 12000 do foundWord:=false:
for i to 9 do if not foundWord then theWord:=theString[reader+1..reader+i]:
if member(theWord, dictionary) then foundWord:=true:
theString:=op(theString), op(translation[theWord]):
reader:=reader+i: fi: od: if not foundWord
then print(reader, theString[reader+1..reader+20]): fi:
if times mod 100 = 0 then print(times, nops(theString)): fi: od:
```

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